

ENSURING NATIONAL SPIRITUAL SECURITY UNDER GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. *The peculiarity of the process of globalization is that it has become a very sharp weapon of ideological influence, serving the interests of various political forces and centers in the current environment, as any sane person can certainly observe.*

Key words: *Globalization, state, world, region, development, area, country, process, phenomenon, people, integration, cooperation, foreign investment.*

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДУХОВНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ

Аннотация. *Своеобразие процесса глобализации состоит в том, что он стал очень острым оружием идеологического воздействия, обслуживающим интересы различных политических сил и центров в современных условиях, что наверняка может наблюдать любой здравомыслящий человек.*

Ключевые слова: *Глобализация, государство, мир, регион, развитие, территория, страна, процесс, явление, народ, интеграция, сотрудничество, иностранные инвестиции.*

Social changes in the global space have caused certain changes in the content of cultural identity, language, art, and spiritual categories, which are the main elements of the national identity of each nation and various ethnic-territorial units, and the process of globalization in secret.

This issue is becoming more acute. As a result of the globalization, integration, and information of society and scientific and technical progress, the rapidly developing intellectual potential of humanity, while serving to improve the economies of peoples, nations, and peoples living in different countries, is indifferent to the process of national identity (awareness of national identity) of peoples. As a result, it will not be possible to fill its place with anything. When talking about the main reason why the process of globalization is entering our lives more and more quickly and deeply, it should be recognized that today the development and prosperity of any country is so closely connected not only with its near and far neighbors, but also with other regions and regions on a global scale, that any country It is not difficult to understand that staying away from this process will not lead to positive results. So, just like any phenomenon has its positive and negative side, the process of globalization is no exception. That's why "local", "regional" and "global" changes will have a positive or negative impact on the future fate of the nation. [1, -B. 676-688]. Currently, it is extremely sharp and comprehensive influence can be seen and felt in almost all areas. In particular, the strengthening of integration and cooperation between countries and peoples, the creation of facilities for the free movement of foreign investments, capital and goods, the labor force, the creation of many new jobs, the advancement of modern communication and information technologies, scientific achievements rapid spread, harmonization of different values on a universal basis, a new quality of communication between civilizations, increased opportunities for mutual assistance during environmental disasters - naturally, all this is achieved due to globalization. The relationship between the individual and the society, the education of a perfect person, a perfect person was considered as a problem in

every era. Therefore, the formation of a spiritually mature person is the main goal of every era. [2, -B. 29-32].

The reality of life shows that any product of development can be used for two purposes - for good and for evil. Man has an evil nature. Virtues in man are qualities acquired for the benefit. [3, -B. 597-605]. If we look at the history of humanity and the development of its thinking gradually, we can see that there has been a struggle between good ideas and teachings that call people to perfection and high goals in life, and evil and harmful ideas. We can see that this struggle continues today. Therefore, the relevance of the topic can be explained by the following factors:

First of all, the peculiarity of the process of globalization is that, in the present conditions, it has become a very sharp weapon of ideological influence, serving the interests of various political forces and centers.

Secondly, in the context of globalization, the scale of threats to spirituality is increasing. Under the guise of the "popular culture" phenomenon, they multiply like mushrooms after the rain.

Thirdly, in the current era of the so-called information age, the spirituality of young people cannot be protected from various spiritual threats by prohibitions.

Fourth, globalization is currently leading to the globalization of education. This requires serious attention to preserving the peculiarities of the educational process.

Fifth, analysis of the factors of ensuring national moral security in the conditions of globalization is becoming more important than ever. As the object of this issue, it is possible to refer to national consciousness, awareness of national identity, strengthening the spirit of respect for the national-spiritual heritage, patriotic feelings.

Some foreign politicians and figures who don't understand or don't want to understand this historical fact are trying to teach us not only about politics or economy, but also about spirituality, and forcefully introduce views that are foreign to our ancient way of life and spiritual world.

The malicious attitude of such forces, their underlying interests, and the fact that they are trying to implement these interests with various methods and means, cannot help but worry all of us. Our President writes on this issue: "Why, many thousand years of human experience shows that violent and aggressive forces in the world want to subjugate and subjugate any nation or country and take its wealth. If he wants to occupy it, first of all, he tries to disarm it, that is, to separate it from its greatest wealth, its national values, history, and spirituality". [4, -B. 42-45] Consequently, any threat directed against spirituality will inevitably become one of the serious threats to the security of the country, its national interests, and the future of a healthy generation, and ultimately lead to a crisis in society.

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Nowadays, the process of globalization is a very complex phenomenon. Due to the fact that its influence on the economy, politics and spirituality of different countries is even more complex, two groups in the world are in competition with each other in relation to it; groups of globalists and anti-globalists emerged. Whether a person wants it or not, he is in the process of direct socialization with nature and society, and events express his attitude to events. [5, -B. 113-115].

If globalization is firmly formed under the influence of the inner world of young people, the ability to think, and national values, then the feelings of patriotism and national responsibility of young people will be strong.

Supporters of globalization are called globalists. Among them there are more statesmen, politicians, industrialists and businessmen.

Opponents of globalization are called anti-globalists, and among them there are more representatives of leftist forces, trade unions and youth organizations. On the territory of the CIS, anti-globalists are active in the territory of the Russian Federation, they gather to hold various conferences and seminars.

In the middle of the 20th century, after the organization of globalization became stronger, this process itself accelerated sharply and took on a violent tone. The strengthening of this organization can be seen in the example of the establishment of the World Trade Organization, the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the European Development and Reconstruction Bank.

In response to the acceleration and intensification of globalization, the activities of anti-globalists have also increased. They began to oppose not only the negative consequences of globalization, but also it itself.

For example, the Russian philosopher and writer A. Zinoviev said so in his speech at the conference "Vectors of Anti-globalization". "Globalization is the new world war. It is a new type of world war.

It is a new type of world war. "I don't see any other way to survive in this war than resistance. Only resistance!" Joseph Stiglitz's opinion is as follows: "Globalization has the best potential for improving people's lives, including the lives of people in developing countries. Some of its directions are present. For example, the globalization of science has led to health care and the life extension of people [6.-B.-11].

Jagdish Bhagwati evaluates globalization as an economic reality: "it includes trade, direct investments, activities of transnational corporations, financial flows between countries, and international migrations." The impact of globalization on different countries is also different. This situation is related to the economic information, moral potential, and politics of the countries of the world. In order to reduce the negative impact of such processes taking place in the world on each country and strengthen the positive impact, it is necessary to understand the essence of this phenomenon and study its features. So, in conclusion, it should be said that every social phenomenon has its positive and negative sides, and the process of globalization is no exception. Currently, its extremely sharp and comprehensive influence can be seen and felt in almost all areas. In particular, the strengthening of integration and cooperation between countries and peoples, the creation of facilities for the free movement of foreign investments, capital and goods, the labor force, the creation of many new jobs, the advancement of modern communication and information technologies, scientific achievements rapid spread, harmonization of different values on a universal basis, a new quality of communication between civilizations, increased opportunities for mutual assistance during environmental disasters - naturally, all this is achieved due to globalization.

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